

Supporting Information for

Tuning of Molecular Plasmons in Anthracene by Peripheral Functionalization

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1. Materials

Anthracene (99 %) (**1**) was purchased from Thermo Fisher scientific, dimethyl anthracene-1,8-dicarboxylate (95 %) (**2**), 9-methylanthracene (98 %) (**6**) and copper(I) cyanide (98 %) were purchased from TCI, 9,10-dibromoanthracene (95 %), 9-bromoanthracene (97 %) and 2,6-dibromoanthraquinone were purchased from Fluorochem, n-BuLi (1.6 M and 2.5 M in hexanes), dimethyl carbonate (99 %), N-methylpyrrolidone (reagent grade, 99 %), zinc (dust, <10 μm , $\geq 98\%$), ammonium hydroxide solution (ACS reagent, 28.0-30.0% NH_3 basis), iodomethane (purum, $\geq 99.0\%$), lithium carbonate (ACS reagent, $\geq 99.0\%$), N,N-dimethylformamide ($\geq 99.8\%$, anhydrous), Calcium hydride (reagent grade, 95%), phenylboronic acid (95 %) and tetrakis(triphenylphosphine)palladium(0) (99 %) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Diethyl ether and tetrahydrofuran (THF) were distilled from sodium-benzophenone ketyl. Silica gel (particle size 35-75 μm) from Sigma Aldrich was used for column chromatography. Thin-layer chromatography was performed on Merck TLC-plates silica gel 60, F-254. Deuterated solvents for NMR measurements DMSO-d_6 , and CDCl_3 were purchased from Eurisotop.

2. Syntheses

2.1. Synthesis of methyl anthracene-9-carboxylate (**3**)

The methyl anthracene-9-carboxylate (**3**) was synthesized following the literature procedure,¹ as graphically shown in Scheme S1. Briefly, 9-Bromoanthracene (0.8mmol, 205 mg) was dried in a Schlenk flask for 1 hr. To this flask 2 mL Diethyl ether was added and stirred for 20 mins, the mixture was cooled to 0°C. n-BuLi (1.2 eq., 0.384 mL, 2.5 M in hexanes) was added dropwise over a span of 10-15 mins. The mixture was stirred for 20 mins at this temperature and cooled to -78°C using an acetone/liquid nitrogen mixture. While at -78 °C, a degassed solution of 2 eq. of Dimethyl carbonate (1.6 mmol, 0.2ml) in 2 mL diethyl ether was added dropwise. The mixture was allowed to warm up to 0°C over 6 hrs. Afterwards, 0.2 mL of degassed acetic acid was added dropwise. The resultant mixture was extracted with DCM and washed with Brine(3x). The Crude mixture was purified by column chromatography on SiO_2 (Hexanes: DCM: 1:1) to isolate the desired product methyl anthracene-9-carboxylate (46.2 mg, 24 %) as a light-yellow solid. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.54 (s, 1H), 8.02 (ddd, $J = 6.58, 2, 2$ Hz, 4H), 7.52 (dddd, $J = 9.4, 7.8, 6.5, 1.1$ Hz, 4H), 4.18 (s, 3 H), ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) 170.57,131.47,129.93,129.11,128.99,128.21,127.49, 125.97,125.52 and 53.10. For the full ^1H -NMR spectrum see section 5.10. MS (APCI): m/z $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ calculated for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2$: 237.27; found 236.9.

Scheme S1. Synthesis of methyl anthracene-9-carboxylate (**3**)

2.2. Synthesis of dimethyl anthracene-9,10-dicarboxylate (**4**)

The dimethyl anthracene-9,10-dicarboxylate (**4**) was synthesized following the literature procedure,¹ as graphically shown in Scheme S2. Briefly, to suspension of 9,10-dibromoanthracene (1 g, 2.98 mmol) in dry Et₂O (10 mL) *n*-BuLi (4.09 mL, 6.55 mmol, 1.6 M in hexanes) was added dropwise at 0 °C and the reaction mixture was stirred for 30 min. The reaction mixture was cooled to -78 °C and 5 mL Et₂O solution of dimethyl carbonate (1 mL, 11.9 mmol) was added dropwise, and the reaction mixture was stirred for 6 h while slowly warmed to 0 °C, quenched with deoxygenated acetic acid (0.39 mL, 6.85 mmol). Water (20 mL) was added, and the water layer was extracted with DCM (3 x 20 mL). The organic layer was dried, solvent was removed, and the residue was purified by column chromatography on SiO₂ (50 % DCM in hexanes) to afford dimethyl anthracene-9,10-dicarboxylate (206 mg, 42 %) as light-yellow solid. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.99 (dd, *J* = 6.8, 3.2 Hz, 4H), 7.56 (dd, *J* = 6.8, 3.2 Hz, 4H), 4.19 (s, 6H) ppm. For the full ¹H-NMR spectrum see section 5.10. MS (APCI): *m/z* [M+H]⁺ calculated for C₁₈H₁₄O₄: 295.09; found: 295.0.

Scheme S2. Synthesis of dimethyl anthracene-9,10-dicarboxylate (**4**)

2.3. Synthesis of dimethyl anthracene-2,6-dicarboxylate (**5**)

The dimethyl anthracene-2,6-dicarboxylate (**4**) was synthesized following the literature procedure,^{2,3} as graphically shown in Schemes S3.

Scheme S3. Overall Synthesis of dimethyl anthracene-2,6-dicarboxylate (**5**). (i) CuCN, NMP, 190 °C, 8 hrs., (ii) H₂SO₄, 160 °C, 6 hrs. (iii) Zn, NH₄OH, 100 °C, 4 hrs. and (iv) Li₂CO₃, CH₃I, DMF, 16 hrs.

Scheme S3a. Synthesis of 2,6-Dicyano-9,10-anthraquinone

A mixture of copper(I) cyanide (2.45 g, 27.3 mmol) and 2,6-dibromoanthracene-9,10-dione (2.5 g, 6.83 mmol) in N-methylpyrrolidone (30 mL) was heated to 190 °C for 8 hrs. (Scheme S3a), then cooled to room temperature and precipitated in water (40 mL). A solid dark compound was filtered and washed with saturated solution of EDTA (3 x 20 mL) to eliminate residual copper. After washing with EDTA solution until complete discoloration, the powder was washed again with water (3 x 20 mL) to give 2,6-dicyano-9,10-anthraquinone as a brown solid (1.5 g, 85 % yield), which was used without further purification. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 8.61 (d, *J* = 35.5, Hz, 2H), 8.34 (s, 2H), 7.73 (s, 2H) ppm.

Scheme S3b. Synthesis of 2,6-anthraquinone dicarboxylic acid

To a suspension of 2,6-dicyano-9,10-anthraquinone (1.5 g, 5.8 mmol) in water (10 mL) was slowly added sulfuric acid (15 mL) under vigorous stirring (Scheme S3b). The mixture was heated to 160 °C for 6 h and then cooled to room temperature. The mixture was poured into water (20 mL) and stirred for 20 min, then filtered and washed with water (3 x 20 mL) to give 2,6-anthraquinone dicarboxylic acid as a pale brown powder (1.34 g, 78 % yield), which was used without further purification. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.54 (s, 2H), 8.31 (d, *J* = 6.8, Hz, 2H), 8.20 (d, *J* = 7.7, Hz, 2H) ppm.

Scheme S3c. Synthesis of anthracene-2,6-dicarboxylic acid

A mixture of 2,6-anthraquinone dicarboxylic acid (1.34 g, 4.5 mmol), Zn powder (4.18 g, 63.8 mmol) and concentrated aqueous ammonia (35 mL) was refluxed for 4 hrs. (Scheme S3c). Additional ammonia (35 mL) was added dropwise throughout the heating. The mixture was then cooled, and vacuum filtered, and the filtrate was acidified by dropwise addition of 12 M HCl to

give a yellow precipitate. The precipitate was collected by vacuum filtration and air-dried to give anthracene-2,6-dicarboxylic acid as yellow solid (0.96 g, 80%), which was used without further purification.

Scheme S3d. Synthesis of dimethyl anthracene-2,6-dicarboxylate

A suspension of anthracene-2,6-dicarboxylic acid (266 mg, 1 mmol), methyl iodide (1.41 g, 10 mmol), and lithium carbonate (738 mg, 10 mmol) in dry N,N-dimethylformamide (15 mL) was stirred overnight at room temperature (Scheme S3d). The mixture was added to 1 M aq. HCl (30 mL), and the resulting yellow precipitate was collected by vacuum filtration and air-dried. The residue was purified by column chromatography on SiO_2 (50 % DCM in hexanes) to afford dimethyl anthracene-2,6-dicarboxylate (241 mg, 81 %) as light-yellow solid. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.82 (s, 2H), 8.59 (s, 2H), 8.10-8.03 (m, 4H) ppm. MS (APCI): m/z $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ calculated for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$: 295.09; found 294.8.

3. Experimental methods

3.1. NMR spectroscopy

NMR spectra were recorded in 5 mm Norell NMR tubes on a VNMRs 600 MHz spectrometer (600 MHz for ^1H ; 150 MHz for ^{13}C , Varian, Inc., Palo Alto, CA, USA) Bruker Ascend 400 (400 MHz for ^1H ; 100 MHz for ^{13}C) in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$, and CDCl_3 as solvents. Coupling constants (J) were recorded in Hertz with multiplicities explained by the following abbreviations: s = singlet, d = doublet, t = triplet, q = quartet, dd = double of doublets, hept = heptets, m = multiplet.

3.2. Mass spectrometry

The mass spectrometry was carried out using volatile Atmospheric Pressure Chemical Ionization (vAPCI) combined with Advion Interchim Scientific®'s expression® Compact Mass Spectrometer (CMS). The monoisotopic mass of $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ was recorded.

3.2. Absorption spectroscopy

Absorption spectrum of neutral and radical species was recorded using Agilent 8453 UV-vis diode array absorption spectrometer (190-1100 nm). For radical anion ($2^{\cdot-}$) we used Jasco V-670 UV-Vis/NIR absorption spectrometer with resolution 2 nm and scan speed 1000 nm/min in range 200 -1700 nm.

3.3. Determination of molar absorption coefficient of neutral anthracenes

Approximately 2 mg of each compound was weighed on the precision scale and dissolved in Acetonitrile. UV-vis-NIR absorption spectra were measured on a Jasco V-670 UV-Vis/NIR absorption spectrometer at room temperature with resolution 0.2nm and speed 40 nm.min⁻¹ in range 200-600nm using a quartz 1 cm cuvette.

3.4. Electrochemistry

Supporting electrolyte (for electrochemistry) tetrabutylammonium perchlorate (TBAP) (for electrochemical analysis, $\geq 99.0\%$) and tetrabutyl ammonium hexafluorophosphate (TBAPF₆) (for electrochemical analysis, $\geq 99.0\%$) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and stored under an inert atmosphere (glove box) prior to use. Acetonitrile was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and pretreated with molecular sieves 4A purchased from Alfa Aesar (activated at 270 °C). The pretreated acetonitrile was then distilled under an inert atmosphere over CaH_2 and de-gassed prior to experiments.

Cyclic voltammograms and differential pulse voltammetry were recorded using a CH Instruments CHI660E electrochemical workstation. To determine the first reduction potential, 5 mM solutions of anthracene and the derivatives in 0.1 M TBAPF₆ in acetonitrile were prepared, in case of compound (**5**) we used a 2mM solution in THF was used due to its poor solubility in Acetonitrile. Solutions were handled and stored under inert conditions prior to measurements. Electrochemistry experiments were performed using a three-electrode system, consisting of Pt

disc as the working electrode, Ag/AgNO₃ (0.01 M in 0.1 M TBAPF₆ in acetonitrile contained in a glass tube fitted with a porous Vycor glass frit) as reference electrode and Pt mesh as a counter electrode. All electrodes were well separated by porous frits. The measurements were carried out in inert atmosphere (Argon), sealing of the three-electrode system using septa and keeping an over pressure using a Schlenk line.

3.5. Spectro-electrochemistry

Cuvettes for spectro-electrochemistry (SEC) experiments were cleaned using 1M HCl, thoroughly rinsed with distilled water, ethanol and acetone respectively, and dried in oven at 120 °C prior to the measurements. Transparent conducting electrode, ITO (Tin-doped Indium Oxide) coated glass (7 x 50 x 0.7 mm) 4-8 Ω was purchased from Delta Technologies, USA. The ITO coated glass was cleaned by mild sonication (~10 min.) in a dilute neutral detergent (Extran® MA 02), followed by rinsing with distilled water, ethanol and acetone and air drying under ambient conditions.

Figure S1 shows a schematic diagram of the experimental setup used in a typical SEC experiment. A three-electrode system consisting of ITO (Tin-doped Indium Oxide) as working electrode, Ag wire as pseudo reference electrode and Pt mesh as a counter electrode were used in the measurements. The measurements were performed in an undivided 1 cm quartz cell. 5 mM solutions of compounds (1), (2), (3) and a 16 mM solution of compound (4) in 0.5 M TBAP in acetonitrile was used as the electrolyte, for compound 5 a 2 mM solution in 0.5 M TBAP in THF was used and the measurements were carried out under an inert atmosphere (Argon). In a typical experiment, a differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) measurement was first used to identify the first reduction potential of the studied anthracene. During the SEC experiment the changes in the

Figure S1. Scheme of experimental setup used in the spectro-electrochemistry measurements.

absorption spectra of the solution near the ITO surface were monitored following application of a potential step to the first reduction potential of the anthracene (determined earlier in the DPV measurement), onto the ITO electrode. The changes in the absorption spectra were recorded every 0.5 seconds for at least 2 min. using Agilent 8453 UV-vis diode array absorption spectrometer in a kinetic mode.

3.6. Reference electrode calibration

Ag wire pseudo-reference electrode was calibrated using a Ferrocene/Ferrocenium (Fc/Fc⁺) couple in 0.5 M TBAP in acetonitrile electrolyte solution, using the same experimental configuration as described in Section 3.5. The measured half-wave potential of the Fc/Fc⁺ couple was found at $E_{1/2}^0 = + 0.2015\text{V}$ vs. Ag wire. The standard potential $E_{1/2}^0$ for Fc/Fc⁺ couple in acetonitrile is reported at +0.64 V vs. the Normal Hydrogen Electrode (NHE).⁴ Based on this

Figure S2. Result of the calibration measurement of the Fc⁺/Fc couple using Ag pseudo-reference electrode in 0.5 M TBAP acetonitrile solution.

result, in the main text the potentials reported vs. NHE electrode were calculated from the experimental half-wave potentials measured vs. Ag wire ($E_{1/2}^0(\text{Ag})$), using an expression: $E_{1/2}^0(\text{NHE}) = E_{1/2}^0(\text{Ag}) + (0.64 - 0.2015\text{V})$.

3.7. Determination of molar extinction coefficient of anion radicals

Molar extinction coefficient of the studied anion radicals was determined by combination of chrono-coulometry and chrono-absorptiometry experiments. In chrono-coulometry experiment the amount of charge passed across the electrode-solution interface following a potential step is described by Anson equation, Eq.(1):⁵

$$Q = \frac{2nFAD_A^{1/2}C_A t^{1/2}}{\pi^{1/2}} = B_1 t^{1/2} \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

In Eq. (1) F is Faraday constant ($F = 96,485 \text{ C/mol}$) A is the area of the (planar) electrode in cm^2 and C_A is the concentration of the compound being reduced in mol/cm^3 . In chrono-absorptiometry the change in the absorbance of the charged species following a potential step is expressed by Eq. (2):⁵

$$Abs = \frac{2\varepsilon_B D_A^{1/2} C_A t^{1/2}}{\pi^{1/2}} = B_2 t^{1/2} \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

In Eq. (2) ε_B is the molar extinction coefficient of the anion radical.

In a typical experiment, chrono-coulometry and chrono-absorptiometry measurements were performed using the experimental setup shown in Fig. S1. The measured temporal changes of charge and absorbance were plotted as a function of $t^{1/2}$ for $t < 1 \text{ s}$ and fitted with Eqs. (1) and (2), respectively to determine the values of the slopes B_1 and B_2 . The molar extinction coefficient of the anion radical was then calculated using Eq(3) (assuming $n = 1$):

$$\varepsilon_B = nFA(B_2/B_1) \quad \text{Eq. (3)}$$

In the experiments, the potential control and the Q monitoring were realized by CH Instruments CHI660E electrochemical workstation. In the chrono-coulometry experiment a data point was collected on average every 2 ms; i.e., ~ 500 experimental points were collected within 1 s. In the chrono-absorptiometry measurements, a data point was collected on average every 13 ms (3 ms integration time); i.e., ~ 75 experimental points were collected within 1 s. The changes in the absorbance were monitored by Ocean optics USB200 UV-Vis fiber optics spectrometer (190 – 1000 nm) with Deuterium & Tungsten Halogen light source DH-2000 (Ocean Optics) light source. The measurements were performed for anthracenes (**1**), (**2**) and (**5**), which showed reversible redox characteristic (see Fig. 1 in the main text). For each compound the experiment was performed at least three times to obtain a standard deviation of the ε_B .

4. Computational methods

4.1. Molecular and electronic structure of anthracenes

Ground and excited state properties of anthracene and its derivatives were calculated using Gaussian package 16. A hybrid function B3LYP^{6,7} with a basis set 6-31+G(d)⁸⁻¹⁰ were used for optimization of the ground state geometry and studies of the excited states characteristics (TD-DFT) of the neutral and negatively charged compounds. A UKS formalism was used for anionic species. The ground state was optimized using a D3 empirical dispersion correction,¹¹ to account for Van der Waals (vdW) interactions. Typically, the properties of the lowest 20 excited states were calculated. Solvent effects were incorporated using conductor-like polarizable continuum model, (CPCM)^{12, 13} with acetonitrile/THF as a solvent. Vibrationally resolved absorption characteristics of selected excitations were calculated using IMDHO (Independent Mode Displaced Harmonic Oscillator) model,¹⁴ implemented in Orca program suite.¹⁵

4.2. Calculation of reduction and oxidation potentials

Oxidation and reduction and potentials of the studied anthracenes shown in Table 2 of the main text were calculated using an approach described previously.¹⁶⁻¹⁸ Briefly, a Born-Haber cycle connecting the electron transfer reaction in the gas and the solution phases was constructed (see example for the reduction reaction in Fig S3). The Gibbs free energy of the reduction reaction in solution ($\Delta G_{red, liq}^{\circ}$) was next calculated using Eq. (4) from the Gibbs free energy of reduction reaction in the gas phase ($\Delta G_{red, gas}^{\circ}$) and the free energies of solvation of the neutral ($\Delta G_{solv, 0}^{\circ}$) and reduced ($\Delta G_{solv, -1}^{\circ}$) anthracene, obtained from DFT calculations:

$$\Delta G_{red, liq}^{\circ} = \Delta G_{red, gas}^{\circ} + \Delta G_{solv, -1}^{\circ} - \Delta G_{solv, 0}^{\circ} \quad \text{Eq. (4)}$$

The standard reduction potential is then calculated using Eq. (5):

$$E_{liq}^{\circ}(0/-1) = \Delta G_{red, liq}^{\circ} / -nF \quad \text{Eq. (5),}$$

where number of exchanged electrons (assumed $n = 1$) and F is the Faraday constant. The reduction potentials calculated using Eq. (5) were converted to NHE scale by adding a scaling constant of 4.43.¹⁶ In calculating the Gibbs free energies $\Delta G_{red, gas}^{\circ}$, $\Delta G_{solv, 0}^{\circ}$, and $\Delta G_{solv, -1}^{\circ}$ the same

Figure S3. Born-Haber cycle associated with one electron reduction of anthracene. Symbols $[An]^0$ and $[An]^{-1}$ represent a neutral anthracene and its anion radical, respectively.

level of theory and solvation model CPCM was used as described in section 4.1. For the molecule (5), the solvent was modelled as THF for consistency with the experimental measurements.

4.3. Quantification of plasmonicity

In TDDFT calculations of the transition density of an electronic excitation by Gaussian software package we used an internal option IOp(9/40=4). Subsequently, we used Multifwn 3.8 software¹⁹ to generate the transition density volumetric data in the Gaussian cube format with a default grid box size (6 a.u. padding around the molecule) and the highest resolution option (nearest cuboid equivalent of 121^3 grid points). From the first 20 excited states we analysed the transitions with oscillator strengths ≥ 0.015 . An in-house Fortran code was used to calculate the Plasmonicity Index (PI), Plasmonicity energy (E_{plas}) and modified Generalized plasmonicity index ($mGPI$) following the definitions shown in Eqs.(1), (2) and (3) in the main text.

While calculating the values of PI for the studied anthracenes we observed a practical limitation of the PI related to the numerical integration. The integrand in the numerator of PI contains only the induced potential $v_{ind,I}$. In contrast, in $E_{plas,I}$ (and thus in the numerators of GPI and $mGPI$) the integrand contains a product $v_{ind,I} \rho_I$. While ρ_I is confined within the immediate vicinity of the molecule and quickly decays to zero away from the molecule, the potential $v_{ind,I}$ extends far beyond the molecule and exhibits very slow decay dominated by the dipole $1/r^2$ asymptotics. We illustrate this with isosurface and 1D line slice plots for two excitations in anthracene in Figures S4, S5. Thanks to the decay of ρ_I , the product $v_{ind,I} \rho_I$ is also confined to the vicinity of the molecule, simplifying the evaluation of $E_{plas,I}$ and $mGPI$.

To numerically converge the PI value, one thus needs to extend the volumetric box by tens of Ångstroms, which due to the need to evaluate $v_{ind,I}(r)$ on a large grid significantly increases the computational cost. In our calculations, we have partially circumvented this problem by using separate numerical grids for evaluation of $\rho_I(r)$ and $v_{ind,I}(r)$. Density is fully captured by the volumetric box described above. Using the same box, we have also evaluated the inner part of the induced potential. This was then extended by a coarser volumetric box (with tripled grid spacing) extending by extra 30 a.u. In this region, the coarser grid is fully justified, as the potential is changing smoothly and slowly dominated by the simple $1/r^2$ asymptotics. Furthermore, we took advantage of these asymptotics and extrapolated the value of PI to an infinite integration volume as shown in Figure S6 below. This technique leads to robust and numerically stable PI values with negligible dependence on the grid choice for the inner integration.

Figure S4. Isosurface plots of the transition density and the induced potential for the 1st and 5th electronic excitation in anthracene shown on the same spatial scale. In all plots, the isosurface values are chosen at 0.1, 0.05 and 0.03 times the maximum value.

While we have circumvented the problem of computational cost of the numerical integration in PI , conceptually a problem remains that PI is sampling regions vastly extending beyond the molecule and is thus sensitive to the treatment of this extraneous volume, especially if one considers solvent effects using dielectric continuum models.

Figure S5. 1D line sections of transition density (top) and the induced potential (bottom) for the 1st and 5th electronic excitation in anthracene shown on the same spatial scale of 50 Bohr.

Figure S6. Extrapolation of plasmonic index (PI) for the 1st and 5th electronic excitation in anthracene to infinite volumetric box size. The individual PI values were calculated for volumetric boxes with padding around the molecule ranging from 6 to 106 a.u.

5. Results

5.1. Radical-radical coupling during electrochemistry

As shown in Fig. 1b in the main text, the cyclic voltammograms of compounds (3) and (4) show distinct irreversible features. We attribute this observation to an electron transfer followed by a rapid chemical reaction, as shown in Scheme S5 for (3). After one electron reduction, the generated anion radical may undergo dimerization, forming a stable dianion, which may subsequently disproportionate to form [9,9'-bianthracene]-10,10'(9H,9'H)-diylidenedimethanone. In the case of anthracene (4) we propose that a similar reaction may yield an ylidenemethanone radical compound. This type of reaction can be expected for the 9 or 9,10 substituted anthracenes as the substitution in these positions increases the reactivity of the radical anion.^{20 21} In other derivatives and the anthracene the extra electron introduced by electrochemical reduction is highly delocalized across the anion radical and is not coupled directly to the carboxy methyl functional group.²²

Scheme S5. Proposed mechanism of electron transfer-induced radical-radical coupling of (3).

5.2. Differential pulse voltammetry

The peak potentials related to oxidation and reduction process were determined by Differential Pulse Voltammetry. The results for compounds (1) to (5) are summarized in Figure S7. The observed sharp peaks for all the derivatives were consistent with one electron reduction or oxidation. In the case of compound (5) we were unable to observe the oxidative potentials because of the limited THF electrochemical window.

Figure S7. Differential pulse voltammogram (DPV) for one electron oxidation (a) and reduction (b) of anthracenes in 0.1 M TBAPF₆, (1)-(4) (5 mM) in Acetonitrile (ACN) and (5) (~2 mM) in THF. WE; Pt disk, RE: 10 mM Ag/AgNO₃ in 0.1M TBAPF₆ (ACN) and CE: Pt wire.

5.3. Calculated reduction and oxidation potentials

The redox potentials calculated using the approach described in section 4.2 are summarized in Table S1. The calculated potentials are in a good agreement with the experimentally measured values with differences ranging from +0.078 V to +0.24 V and a Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of 0.1432 V. The theoretical Gibbs free energies calculated for the one electron reduction process are summarized in Table S2. The second reduction potentials and oxidation potentials are summarized in Tables S3 and S5, respectively. The corresponding Gibbs energies of one and two electron reduction and oxidation potentials are summarized in Tables S4 and S6, respectively.

$$\Delta G_{red,gas}^{\circ}$$

Table S1: Comparison of experimental and calculated standard first reduction potentials, $E_{liq}^{\circ}(0/-1)$. All potentials are in Volts.

Compound	Solvent	vs Ag/AgNO ₃ (experimental)	vs NHE (experimental)	vs SCE (Calculated)	vs NHE (Calculated)
1	ACN	-2.31	-1.77	-1.89	-1.64
2	ACN	-1.84	-1.29	-1.30	-1.06
3	ACN	-1.93	-1.39	-1.51	-1.27
4	ACN	-1.75	-1.21	-1.30	-1.05
5	THF	-1.81	-1.27	-1.44	-1.19

Table S2: DFT calculated gas phase Gibbs free energies associated with one electron reduction of anthracenes.

Compound	Solvation: CPCM	$G_{red,gas}^{\circ}$ (Hartree)		$\Delta G_{solv,-1}^{\circ} - \Delta G_{solv,0}^{\circ}$ (Hartree)	$\Delta G_{red,gas}^{\circ}$ (Hartree)
		Neutral (RB3LYP)	Radical (UB3LYP)		
1	ACN	-539.3892714	-539.4147059	-0.059155838	-0.084590356
2	ACN	-995.0801213	-995.130227	-0.05595462	-0.106060386
3	ACN	-767.2252837	-767.2653845	-0.058254497	-0.098355228
4	ACN	-995.0676045	-995.1193887	-0.054570954	-0.106355144
5	THF	-995.0937682	-995.1453397	-0.049626128	-0.10119763

Table S3: Calculated second reduction potentials. All potentials are in Volts.

Anthracene	Solvent	vs SCE (Calculated)	vs NHE (Calculated)
1	ACN	-2.80	-2.55
2	ACN	-2.09	-1.85
3	ACN	-2.16	-1.91
4	ACN	-1.72	-1.47
5	THF	-2.47	-2.22

Table S4: DFT calculated gas phase Gibbs free energies associated with two electron reduction of anthracenes.

Compound	Solvation: CPCM	$G^{\circ}_{red,gas}$ (Hartree)		$\Delta G^{\circ}_{solv,-2} - \Delta G^{\circ}_{solv,-1}$ (Hartree)	$\Delta G^{\circ}_{red,gas}$ (Hartree)
		Anion Radical (UB3LYP)	Dianion (UB3LYP)		
1	ACN	-539.4147059	-539.2878711	-0.177958267	-0.051123496
2	ACN	-995.130227	-994.961245	-0.246102297	-0.077120283
3	ACN	-767.2653845	-767.1702629	-0.1697724	-0.074650848
4	ACN	-995.1193887	-995.0410492	-0.169130895	-0.090791368
5	THF	-995.1453397	-995.0764134	-0.132227484	-0.063301167

Table S5: Calculated standard oxidation potentials. All potentials are in Volts.

Anthracene	Solvent	vs Ag/AgNO ₃ (experimental)	vs NHE (experimental)	vs SCE (Calculated)	vs NHE (Calculated)
1	ACN	0.91	1.45	1.23	1.47
2	ACN	1.14	1.68	1.53	1.78
3	ACN	1.11	1.65	1.39	1.64
4	ACN	1.26	1.80	1.54	1.79
5	THF	-	-	1.71	1.96

Table S6: DFT calculated gas phase Gibbs free energies associated with one electron oxidation of anthracenes.

Compound	Solvation: CPCM	$G^{\circ}_{red,gas}$ (Hartree)		$\Delta G^{\circ}_{solv,0} - \Delta G^{\circ}_{solv,1}$ (Hartree)	$\Delta G^{\circ}_{red,gas}$ (Hartree)
		Neutral (RB3LYP)	Cationic radical (UB3LYP)		
1	ACN	-539.3892714	-539.1315697	0.058636718	-0.199064968
2	ACN	-995.0676045	-994.8064159	0.0504804	-0.210708205
3	ACN	-767.2252837	-766.9690396	0.051110968	-0.205133126
4	ACN	-995.0676045	-994.8064159	0.0504804	-0.210708205
5	THF	-995.0937682	-994.8285117	0.054693956	-0.210562542

5.4. Molecular structures of neutral and charged anthracenes

When calculating the molecular structures of neutral and anionic forms of the anthracenes by methods summarized in section 4.1., we found that upon charging, some of the anthracenes undergo significant structural changes, particularly in terms of dihedral angles between the anthracene ring system and the substituent ester groups. The results are summarized in Fig. S8. Significant structural changes are observed in the case of (2), where the dihedral angle decrease from 29.12° to 1.59° upon one electron reduction, resulting in a coplanar arrangement of ester with the anthracene ring system. In (3) and (4), the reduction leads to a decrease in the dihedral

Figure S8. Calculated changes in the dihedral angles between ester group and plane of the anthracene derivatives after single electron reduction.

angles of the ester groups, and the anthracene ring undergoes puckering; i.e., it is deformed. These effects are small in (5) as the functional groups are positioned away from the core, inducing no structural strain. These results indicate that one-electron reduction results in complete or near complete planarization in less hindered systems (2) and (5). In systems with meso substitutions, (3) and (4) the planarization is incomplete because of the steric strain, which is accommodated by the deformation of the central anthracene ring.

5.5. Electrostatic surface potentials

Figure S9 shows the results of the Electrostatic Surface Potential (ESP) calculations for neutral and singly charged compounds (1) to (6). The ESP analysis shows that in neutral compounds, the electron-rich regions are found mostly on electronegative atoms of the functional group. In anion radicals the excess electron density is delocalized across the anthracene core and the carbonyl part of the ester functional groups. The core becomes more electron-rich compared to its (diamagnetic) parent due to an increase in aromatic character by the addition of one electron.²³ The surfaces and images were generated using multifwn²⁴ and vmd²⁵ respectively.

Figure S9. Electrostatic potential surface diagram of anthracene and derivatives (1) to (6) obtained from DFT calculations (isovalue 0.001).

5.6. Frontier Molecular Orbitals of radical anions

Figures 10 and 11 show the isosurfaces of frontier molecular orbitals for anion radicals $(1)^{-1}$ to $(5)^{-1}$ obtained by DFT calculations as described in section 4.1. The images were generated using a Multifwn software package with isovalue of 0.04.

Figure S10. Calculated isosurfaces of the frontier MOs for anion radicals $(1)^{-1}$ to $(4)^{-1}$.

Figure S11. Calculated isosurfaces of the frontier MOs for anion radical $(5)^{\bullet-}$.

5.7. The origin of the differences in the energies of the lowest energy excitations in anion radicals

An introduction of the electron withdrawing group (EWG), such as methyl ester carboxylate into the molecular structure is generally expected to lead to stabilization of the HOMO and LUMO orbitals via the electron-withdrawing inductive and mesomeric effects. Our modeling results (see **Fig. 2k-o** in the main text) are consistent with this expectation. In both, the neutral anthracenes and their anion radicals the HOMO and LUMO levels are stabilized. However, our results also show that the LUMO orbitals are significantly more stabilized in the $(\mathbf{2})^{-1}$ and $(\mathbf{5})^{-1}$ derivatives than in $(\mathbf{1})^{-1}$, $(\mathbf{3})^{-1}$ and $(\mathbf{5})^{-1}$. This is most apparent in the α manifold.

To explain this difference, we point to the differences in the molecular structures of the neutral and charged derivatives summarized in **Fig. S8**. As shown in the figure, in all neutral derivatives $(\mathbf{2})$ to $(\mathbf{5})$, as a result of steric hindrance, the ester groups are, to a various extent, twisted out of plane of the anthracene. Upon addition of an electron, the out-of-plane distortions (dihedral angles) are significantly reduced in all derivatives. In the case of $(\mathbf{2})^{-1}$ and $(\mathbf{5})^{-1}$ the anion radicals form nearly planar structures. This allows for an effective electronic conjugation of the π orbitals of the ester groups with the anthracene core. As a result, the anthracene core electrons can effectively delocalize along the extended conjugated structure, stabilizing the corresponding MOs. As can be seen in **Figs. S10** and **S11**, in the case of $(\mathbf{2})^{-1}$ and $(\mathbf{5})^{-1}$ derivatives, the delocalization effect is more pronounced for the LUMO orbitals. Consequently, in the anion radicals of $(\mathbf{2})^{-1}$ and $(\mathbf{5})^{-1}$ the HOMO-LUMO gap is notably reduced relative to the anthracene anion radical $(\mathbf{1})^{-1}$.

The situation is different in the case of derivatives $(\mathbf{3})^{-1}$ and $(\mathbf{4})^{-1}$. Although, in this case the introduction of an electron also leads to the reduction of the out-of-plane distortions of the ester groups, the esters are never fully planarized with the anthracene core (see **Fig. S8**). As a result, the conjugation of the π orbitals of the ester groups with the anthracene core is much weaker. The electronic distortions are in this case dominated by the inductive effect, which more effectively stabilizes occupied orbitals (including HOMO) than the unoccupied orbitals (including LUMO). Therefore, the HOMO - LUMO gap in the anion radical derivatives $(\mathbf{3})^{-1}$ and $(\mathbf{4})^{-1}$ increases relative to the HOMO - LUMO gap in anthracene anion radical $(\mathbf{1})^{-1}$.

To further support the above conclusions, we also modelled the molecular and electronic structure anthracene derivative; 9-methyl anthracene $(\mathbf{6})$. The results, summarized in bottom part of Fig. S8 (molecular structure) and Figs. S14, S16 and S17 (electronic structure) show that in this derivative, where the methyl group is rotated out of plane of the anthracene and is not electronically conjugated with the anthracene core, the low energy absorption band of the anion radical $(\mathbf{6})^{-1}$ is very similar to the absorption band of $(\mathbf{1})^{-1}$.

5.8. Spectral fitting of the isolated absorption bands of anion radicals

To estimate the damping energy Γ , the absorption spectra of the anion radical with higher plasmonicity indexes were analyzed by spectral fitting. In the analysis the experimental spectra were fit by a series of Voigt profiles defined by Eq. (6), using a locally written software.

$$V(x, \sigma, \Gamma) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} G(x', \sigma) L(x - x', \Gamma) dx' \quad \text{Eq. (6),}$$

where

$$G(x, \sigma) = \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{x^2}{2\sigma^2}\right)}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} \quad \text{Eq.(7)}$$

and

$$L(x, \Gamma) = \frac{\Gamma}{\pi(\Gamma^2 + x^2)} \quad \text{Eq.(8)}$$

In the fitting, Γ , σ and x were adjustable parameters. The values of Γ , σ were constrained to be the same for all the profiles. Parameter B (baseline) was allowed to vary between 0 and 0.02. The number of profiles used in the fitting of a single experimental peak was kept to minimum necessary to achieve fit with χ^2 values smaller than 10^{-3} . Only in the case of low energy peaks of anion radicals (**1**)⁻¹ and (**5**)⁻¹ the fitting yielded non-zero Γ values. The best fits for these two cases are shown in Fig. S12. The extracted parameters are summarized in Table S7.

Figure S12. Best fit (red line) of multiple Voigt profiles to the experimental low energy absorption peaks (black dots) of anion radicals $(\mathbf{1})^{-1}$ (a) and $(\mathbf{5})^{-1}$ (b). The green curves show the individual Voigt profiles.

Table S7. Summary of the results of the fit of the Voigt function peaks to the experimental spectra of the anion radicals $(\mathbf{1})^{-1}$ and $(\mathbf{5})^{-1}$

Anion radical.	$(\mathbf{1})^{-1}$	$(\mathbf{5})^{-1}$
Gamma (Γ)	0.105 ± 0.002	0.129 ± 0.003
Sigma (σ)	0.009 ± 0.002	0.008 ± 0.004
χ^2	2.78E-04	2.71E-04
Baseline	0.004 ± 0.001	0.020 ± 0.002
RMS Residual	0.017	0.016

5.9. Characterization of 9-methylanthracene (6)

This section summarizes the results of the characterization of the 9-methylanthracene, compound (6) and its anion radical.

Figure S13. Comparison of the absorption spectra of the neutral anthracene (1) and 9-methyl anthracene (6).

Figure S14. Comparison of the Absorption spectra of the anion radicals of anthracene (1) and 9-methyl anthracene (6), obtained from spectro-electrochemical measurements at first reduction potential.

Figure S15. Cyclic voltammetry of (6) in 0.5 M TBAP Acetonitrile working electrode: ITO, CE: platinum wire and RE: Ag wire. Scan rate was 500 mV/s.

Figure S16. (a) Experimentally measured electronic absorption spectra of neutral (gray traces) and negatively charged (green traces) 9-methylanthracene (6). The red dashed traces show the theoretically (IMDHO) calculated vibrationally resolved electronic absorption spectra of the negatively charged anion radical. (b) photographs of the ITO electrodes before (0) and during (-1) application of the potential. (c) Calculated energies of the molecular orbitals for the neutral and singly negatively charged anthracene (6). The energies of the MOs were calculated at the TDDFT B3LYP/631g+(d) level of theory.

Figure S17. (a) TDDFT calculated electronic absorption spectra of the neutral (gray traces) and singly charged (green traces) 9-methylanthracene (**6**). (b) Transition density of the corresponding transitions of the neutral and charged 9-methylanthracene (**6**).

5.10. mGPI summary for Ag₂₀, charged and neutral anthracenes

Table S8 summarizes the results of the TDDFT calculations of the oscillator strengths, PI , E_{plas} , integrated transition charge density squared ($Itds$) and $mGPI$ values for twenty lowest energy excitations for the Ag₂₀ cluster, charged and neutral anthracene and its derivatives functionalized in -1,8, -9, -9,10 and 2,6 positions with methyl ester carboxylate and in -1,8, -9, and 2,6 with methyl functional group. Only excitations with calculated oscillator strength ≥ 0.015 in anthracenes are included in the table. The values shown in bold are shown in Table 2 in the main text. The $mGPI\ norm.$ represents a value of $mGPI$ normalized with respect to 3.17 eV excitation in Ag₂₀ cluster. The excitations observed in the Ag₂₀ cluster were characterized as plasmonic in number of earlier reports.²⁶⁻³³ The calculated absorption spectrum, transition densities and $mGPI$ values for Ag₂₀ are graphically summarized in Figure S18. The $mGPI\ norm$ values for band edge excitation in the neutral anthracene are included at the end of the Table 8. These excitations are mostly single electron excitations and are expected to have low or no plasmonic character.^{34, 35} Consistent with that expectation, their $mGPI\ norm$ values are 2-3 times lower than the $mGPI\ norm$ values calculated for Ag₂₀ cluster. The $mGPI\ norm$ values calculated for the lowest energy excitations in the negatively charged anthracenes (**1**)⁻¹, (**2**)⁻¹ and (**4**)⁻¹ to (**8**)⁻¹ are ~ 1.5 - 2 x higher than the band-edge excitations in the neutral anthracene and are comparable with the lower energy excitations in Ag₂₀ cluster. As discussed in more detail in the main text, we attribute this observation to the increase in plasmonic character of the excitations in charged anthracene derivatives relative to their neutral forms. This conclusion is consistent with the conclusions of the earlier studies.^{34,35} In the case of (**3**)⁻¹ the low energy excitation has lower plasmonic character than the corresponding excitation in (**1**)⁻¹. The reason for this observation is discussed in the main text.

Table S8. Calculated plasmonic characteristics of Ag₂₀, neutral and charged anthracenes.

Compound	Excit. (eV)	Osc. str.	PI (a.u.)	E _{plas} (a.u.) x1000	It _{ds} (a.u.) x1000	mGPI (a.u.)	mGPI norm.
Ag ₂₀	1.69	0.004	532	2.29	0.26	8.98	0.59
	1.91	0.013	1220	1.60	0.18	9.07	0.59
	2.78	0.030	1003	2.75	0.32	8.67	0.57
	3.17	1.310	7833	14.93	0.98	15.26	1.00
An [•] (1) ⁻¹	1.910	0.186	1806	10.63	1.34	7.93	0.52
	2.209	0.023	311	8.21	1.61	5.09	0.33
	3.356	0.061	749	5.51	0.84	6.58	0.43
	3.389	0.098	3502	2.38	0.19	12.38	0.81
	3.641	0.017	432	2.15	0.38	5.61	0.37
	3.717	0.028	585	1.17	0.21	5.67	0.37
An-1,8-(COOMe) ₂ [•] (2) ⁻¹	1.178	0.169	2793	12.40	1.24	9.97	0.65
	2.113	0.024	371	5.61	1.12	5.01	0.33
	2.380	0.080	1013	7.17	1.03	6.96	0.46
	3.273	0.093	742	8.25	1.32	6.24	0.41
	3.477	0.079	1111	3.57	0.55	6.52	0.43
	3.609	0.071	683	4.18	0.73	5.76	0.38
	3.668	0.051	803	2.57	0.46	5.64	0.37
	3.857	0.016	184	2.49	0.64	3.88	0.25
An-9-(COOMe) [•] (3) ⁻¹	2.265	0.113	1130	11.11	1.47	7.54	0.49
	2.398	0.116	1254	6.75	1.01	6.70	0.44
	3.291	0.049	854	3.48	0.55	6.27	0.41
	3.583	0.015	313	2.00	0.40	5.04	0.33
	3.624	0.033	736	2.41	0.39	6.17	0.40
	3.699	0.111	1787	3.79	0.44	8.67	0.57
	3.781	0.024	512	2.23	0.43	5.23	0.34
	An-9,10-(COOMe) ₂ [•] (4) ⁻¹	1.994	0.025	275	7.19	1.69	4.26
2.463		0.216	1700	9.93	1.36	7.31	0.48
2.503		0.103	1177	5.65	0.90	6.29	0.41
3.472		0.031	699	1.92	0.35	5.43	0.36
3.652		0.070	2539	2.12	0.20	10.52	0.69
3.674		0.074	2781	2.00	0.19	10.73	0.70
An-2,6-(COOMe) ₂ [•] (5) ⁻¹	1.593	0.424	3792	13.66	1.38	9.92	0.65
	2.086	0.099	815	8.22	1.40	5.88	0.39
	2.735	0.048	831	5.08	0.77	6.56	0.43
	2.973	0.082	1606	2.05	0.32	6.35	0.42
	3.884	0.041	1243	0.79	0.15	5.43	0.36

Table S8. Continued.

Compound	Excit. (eV)	Osc. str.	PI (a.u.)	E _{plas} (a.u.) x1000	ltds (a.u.) x1000	mGPI (a.u.)	mGPI norm.
An-9-Me[•] (6)⁻¹	1.899	0.185	1892	10.50	1.30	8.09	0.53
	2.145	0.029	361	8.05	1.58	5.10	0.33
	3.216	0.065	877	4.19	0.71	5.92	0.39
	3.324	0.092	3419	2.38	0.20	12.18	0.80
	3.440	0.037	526	4.65	0.82	5.64	0.37
	3.677	0.022	564	1.27	0.22	5.79	0.38
An-1,8-Me₂[•] (7)⁻¹	1.976	0.197	1790	10.14	1.36	7.45	0.49
	2.199	0.029	379	7.89	1.50	5.24	0.34
	3.063	0.079	1387	4.11	0.54	7.64	0.50
	3.350	0.037	1012	1.89	0.28	6.79	0.44
	3.392	0.069	1833	2.09	0.25	8.30	0.54
	3.404	0.030	494	4.27	0.78	5.45	0.36
An-2,6-Me₂[•] (8)⁻¹	1.848	0.201	2143	10.23	1.22	8.38	0.55
	2.123	0.021	322	8.35	1.63	5.13	0.34
	3.102	0.064	1017	4.03	0.59	6.81	0.45
	3.397	0.085	2738	2.03	0.21	9.78	0.64
	3.745	0.019	186	3.28	0.74	4.44	0.29
An	3.175	0.084	347	16.61	3.41	4.88	0.32
An-1,8-(COOMe)₂	2.947	0.130	539	13.84	2.67	5.18	0.34
An-9-(COOMe)	3.090	0.118	432	16.32	3.31	4.94	0.32
An-9,10-(COOMe)₂	3.031	0.140	459	15.33	3.28	4.67	0.31
An-2,6-(COOMe)₂	2.861	0.120	523	13.88	2.57	5.41	0.35

Figure S18. TDDFT (PBEPBE/Def2TZVP) calculated absorption spectra (black line) with FWHM of 0.2 eV and mGPI (blue vertical lines) calculated for peaks in the low energy region of Ag_{20} with isosurface of transition density (inset) for excitations at 1.69, 1.91, 2.78 and 3.18 eV with isovalue of 0.0001. The three spatial polarizations of excitation at 3.18 eV are shown on the right side of the figure (inset).

The input optimized geometry of Ag_{20} tetrahedral cluster was taken from literature.²⁶ The excited state characteristics were derived using TDDFT for the first 100 excited states using PBEPBE/Def2TZVP level of theory.³⁶

5.1.1. NMR spectra

Figure S19. ^1H NMR spectrum of Methyl anthracene-9-carboxylate (3).

Figure S20. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of Methyl anthracene-9-carboxylate (3).

6. References

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